

EVIDENCE-BASED TOXICOLOGY
An open science journal for environmental health research

Evaluation Report (Acceptance Note) for **TEBT-2023-0009**

Submission information table

Submission Title	Using Machine-Learning to Facilitate Data Extraction for Human Health Chemical Assessments: A Proof-of-Concept Protocol
Submission Reference	TEBT-2023-0009
Handling Editor	Paul Whaley ORCID 0000-0003-4021-0785
Number of Reviewers	3 peer-reviewers + handling editor comments
Submission Type	Method (Protocol) ▾
Preprint DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11042820
Evaluation Stage	Acceptance Note ▾
Evaluation Date	19 Oct 2024
Recommendation	Accept ▾

Acceptance note

Written by the Handling Editor as a summary of the key points from the peer-review process

This manuscript has been accepted for publication by the handling editor Paul Whaley after 2 rounds of revision in response to 2 rounds of editorial triage and 1 round of peer-review.

During triage, the handling editor identified issues around the clarity of the objective of the planned study and the completeness of the planned methods. During peer-review, the evaluators also recommended the authors add information about how they plan to analyse their collected data as it relates to validating the performance of their approach. This information was added by the authors in a comprehensively revised manuscript that the handling editor judged did not need to be re-reviewed.

The evaluation process reinforced the importance of including analysis plans in study protocols and the value of distinguishing exploratory from confirmatory research when describing the goals of a study.

A complete record of the evaluation reports for this submission can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10073180>.